

LEXICOGRAPHIC INTERPRETATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH THE “WHITE” (OQ) SEMANTIC COMPONENT IN THE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE (1981 EDITION)

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ABSTRACT

In the process of language development, its vocabulary also becomes enriched. These changes and developments are associated with the emergence of new lexical units and the obsolescence of some existing ones. As a result, the need to compile explanatory dictionaries arises. In 1981, a two-volume Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language containing approximately 60,000 words and word combinations was published. This thesis analyzes the lexicographic interpretation of phraseological units with the “white” (oq) semantic component in the 1981 edition of the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language.

Following the publication of the dictionary, significant social, political, and economic changes took place in Uzbekistan over the subsequent years. These included the achievement of independence, the granting of state language status to the Uzbek language, the adoption of the Law “On the State Language,” and the expansion of opportunities for linguistic development. Furthermore, economic, political, and cultural relations with developed countries had a substantial impact on the Uzbek lexical system. Such transformations necessitated the creation of a new explanatory dictionary.

As a result, between 2006 and 2008, a five-volume *Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language* was published, containing explanations of more than 80,000 words and word combinations in active usage. In this edition, phraseological units and their interpretations were presented more extensively. Particular attention was also paid to terminology from various fields of science that emerged after Uzbekistan gained independence. This dictionary encompasses the lexical material of the Uzbek language from the early twentieth century to the early twenty-first century.

According to Presidential Decree No. PF-6084 dated October 20, 2020, entitled “*On Measures to Further Develop the Uzbek Language and Improve Language Policy in Our Country*,” linguists were assigned the task of compiling several dictionaries. Among these tasks was the creation of an explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language based on the Latin script [2]. As a result, in 2022, G’afur G’ulom Publishing House published a six-volume explanatory dictionary based on the Latin alphabet, containing over 80,000 words and word combinations. This

dictionary also contributes significantly to enriching the lexical resources of the Uzbek language.

Phraseological units with color semantics occupy a special place in explanatory dictionaries. The 1981 explanatory dictionary primarily focuses on the interpretation of lexical units, namely words and word combinations, and does not provide an extensive semantic analysis of phraseological units. However, phraseological units with color semantics (such as those expressing white, black, red, blue, etc.) play an important role in the Uzbek language and are often associated with folk worldview, culture, and symbolic meanings.

In Uzbek, phraseological units related to colors generally express emotional, symbolic, social, or cultural meanings. The full semantic content of phraseological units with the *white* (*oq*) component is more comprehensively explained in phraseological dictionaries. In the 1981 explanatory dictionary, the semantic characteristics of the lexeme *oq* primarily denote the color of snow, milk, and cotton, which represents its basic denotative meaning. When considering its connotative meanings, the following phraseological units are noteworthy.

The phraseological unit **“to separate white from black”** (*oqni oqqa, qorani qoraga ajratmoq*) [1] is interpreted as expressing justice, correctness, good deeds, and truth. For example: *“We will investigate and separate white from black”* (S. Ahmad, *Hukm*).

The expressions **“to recognize white and black”** (*oq-qorani tanimoq*) and **“to distinguish white from black”** (*oqdan qorani ajratmoq*) are explained as the ability to distinguish between good and bad, friend and enemy, benefit and harm. For example: *“I spent two years in an orphanage, learned literacy, and began to understand white and black to some extent”* (T. Malik, *A Song about a Free Man*).

The phraseological unit **“the white and black of one’s eyes”** (*ko’zining oq-u qorasi*) is interpreted as referring to one’s dearest and only child. This phrase reflects the deep affection traditionally shown toward children in Uzbek culture.

The expression **“white road”** (*oq yo’l*) [1] denotes a safe and trouble-free path. For instance: *“...After reading the notebook, Jahongir wished his son a white road”* (T. Malik, *Falak*).

The phrase **“to wear white”** (*oq kiymoq*) signifies replacing black mourning clothes with white ones after the mourning period ends.

The phraseological unit **“white-hearted”** (*oq ko’ngil*) [1] describes a sincere, kind-hearted, and selfless person: *“This Zebinisa is a rare girl—kind, white-hearted, and compassionate”* (Cho’lpon, *Night and Day*).

The expression **“to milk one’s white milk into white and blue milk into blue”** (*oq sutimni oqqa, ko’k sutimni ko’kka sog’moq*) reflects dissatisfaction with one’s child and renunciation of parental support. This meaning is illustrated in A. Qodiriy’s *O’tkan kunlar*.

The phrase **“white blessing”** (*oq fotiha*) [1] refers to a joyful permission or consent to begin an undertaking: *“Before setting out on a long journey, he went to receive his mother’s white blessing”* (P. Qodirov, *Avlodlar dovoni*).

The expression **“to declare white”** (*oq qilmoq*) conveys the meaning of cursing or renouncing one’s child. This phrase is used in T. Malik’s *Murdalar gapirmaydilar* to emphasize moral condemnation.

The phrase **“one whose bowl has not turned white”** (*kosasi oqarmagan*) [1] has two meanings:

1. a household without a milking cow;
2. lack of prosperity or blessing in one's earnings.

The expression **“one's mouth turned white”** (*og'zi oqarib qoldi*) [557] signifies the acquisition of a milking cow and regular consumption of dairy products (G'. G'ulom).

Conclusion

In conclusion, although phraseological units with color semantics were not analyzed as a separate category in the 1981 *Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language*, they were partially presented as illustrative examples within lexical entries. At the same time, Shavkat Rahmatullayev's phraseological dictionary serves as an important source, offering a more detailed description of the semantic and grammatical features of color-semantic phraseological units, as well as their usage in literary contexts.

References:

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